

LONG-TERM MONITORING OF STRAIN CHANGES IN CFRP USING FBG SENSORS

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1 Introduction

FBG (Fiber Bragg Grating) sensors are one of the promising devices for SHM (Structural Health Monitoring) in CFRP structures. They have some advantages, small size, light weight, and immunity to electromagnetic interference. Since FBGs can measure the strain or temperature changes precisely, the author has applied them to the monitoring of damages or curing in CFRP [1-3]. Also, the FBG have potential to apply the monitoring of CFRP influenced by creep deformation, physical aging, and moisture absorption. This is important to extend the range of application of the FBG as practical monitoring techniques. The authors report a fundamental demonstration about the monitoring of internal strain changes caused by physical aging in CFRP.

2 Strain changes at constant temperature

2.1 Measurement setup

CFRP specimens were manufactured from an intermediate modulus carbon fiber reinforced toughened epoxy prepregs (IM600/#133; Toho Tenax Co. Ltd.) The prepregs was kept at 180°C, 2.5 hours using an autoclave machine. The dimensions of the specimen were 100 mm length and 50 mm width as shown in Figure 1. Optical fiber was embedded into each unidirectional CFRP laminate in directions of 0°, 45°, and 90°. Also, different thickness specimens, 4 plies and 8 plies, and 12 plies were prepared in order to investigate the influence of

the thickness on the strain change. The embedding location of the FBG was the center of the specimen in both in-plane and thickness directions. The configurations of the specimens were summarized in Table 1.

Fig.1 Schematic illustration of specimen with embedded FBG.

Table1 Configuration of specimens

Fiber directions	Embedding locations	Thicknesses (mm)
0°	4 plies, [0 ₂ /OF/0 ₂]	0.503
	8 plies, [0 ₄ /OF/0 ₄]	1.012
	12 plies, [0 ₆ /OF/0 ₆]	1.582
45°	4 plies, [45 ₂ /OF/45 ₂]	0.507
	8 plies, [45 ₄ /OF/45 ₄]	1.018
	12 plies, [45 ₆ /OF/45 ₆]	1.593
90°	4 plies, [90 ₂ /OF/90 ₂]	0.509
	8 plies, [90 ₄ /OF/90 ₄]	1.021
	12 plies, [90 ₆ /OF/90 ₆]	1.598

After the curing, the specimens were placed into the hot oven at 100°C for accelerating the influence of the physical aging. Without mechanical loading and water absorption, strain changes were measured by the FBGs during 30,000 minutes. Though the shape of the spectrum from the FBG was deformed, the strain changes were evaluated by the shift of the spectrum using 12.26 pm/°C. The overshoot of temperature occurred in the hot oven, but temperature was almost uniform, 98 °C to 99 °C after 120 mins had passed. The residual strain after 120 mins was set at reference value of 0 $\mu\epsilon$.

Resin shrinkage will be caused by both physical aging and resin curing if degree of cure was imperfect due to our fabrication process by the autoclave. The DSC curves were obtained by heating rate of 10 °C/min. Figure 2 shows the heat flow changes for the prepreg and the cured CFRP. The exothermal reaction of 91.5 J/g was observed through curing of the prepreg. The degree of cure in the cured CFRP was estimated over 0.95 because the exothermal reaction was almost 0.

Fig.2 DSC curves of prepreg and cured CFRP.

2.2 Results

Figure 3 shows the comparisons of changes in the spectra between 0° specimens and 90° specimens. The spectra in the 90° specimens splits into two peaks due to birefringence effect indicating that the non-axisymmetric strain arises at core of the FBGs. The spectrum shifted to lower wavelength with keeping its shape. On the other hand, the changes in the spectra in the 0° specimens were exceedingly small. The tendency in 45° specimens was roughly intermediate between those of the 0° specimen and 90° specimen. Though axial strains were non-uniform along the FBG, change in the axial strain can be evaluated during because the spectrum shifted with keeping its shape for all our specimens.

Fig.3 Spectral changes for 4 plies specimens.

Figure 4(a) shows the axial residual strain changes for the 90° specimens. The compressive strain increased slowly from 0 to 10,000 mins, and it increased gradually from 10,000 mins to 30,000 mins. The influence of the thickness on the strain change could not be observed by this experiment. There was possibility of continuation of the strain change after 30,000 mins. Figure 4(b) shows the residual strain changes for the 0° specimens.

The strain changes were quite small, and their fluctuation ranges were $\pm 30 \mu\epsilon$. The amount of the strain change was influenced by not only the physical aging but also the stress relaxation of the epoxy resin in the CFRP. The analytical studies or additional experiments are needed for clarification of the details. However, it was expected that the increase in the compressive residual strain was caused by physical aging because the strain in the 90° specimen represents relatively the characteristic of the resin. The amount of strain changes at 30,000 mins were summarized in Table 2.

Table2 Residual strain changes at 30,000 min

	Residual strain changes ($\mu\epsilon$)		
	0° specimen	45° specimen	90° specimen
4 plies	-8.3	-83.5	-242.1
8 plies	-8.4	-75.1	-233.8
12 plies	-8.3	-91.8	-225.4

3 Strain changes in creep test

CFRP specimens were manufactured from same prepreg materials. The dimensions of the specimen were 210 mm length and 25.4 mm width. The stacking sequences of the specimen were $[90]_{16}$ and $[0_2/90_8]_S$. Creep tests were carried out using lever arm creep test machines at 100 °C.

Strain changes in the $[90]_{16}$ specimens were measured by strain gages and extensometer as shown in Figure 5. At 0 MPa, the strain decreased due to physical aging. The average strain at final state of measurement, ϵ_{PA} was -345.6 $\mu\epsilon$. The creep strain at 10 MPa within linear viscoelastic, ϵ_c decreased because the physical aging influences the strain to a greater degree than the stress. Creep strain without physical aging, ϵ' can be estimated by Equation (1) on the assumption that compressive strain due to physical aging at 0 MPa is same as that at 10 MPa.

$$\epsilon' = \epsilon_c - \epsilon_{PA} \quad (1)$$

The creep modulus without physical aging, $E_T(t)$ was calculated by ϵ' as shown in Figure 6. The modulus decreased gradually from 6790 MPa to 6110 MPa.

Strain changes in the $[0_2/90_8]_S$ specimens were measured at 0 MPa. Since the initial stress of 90° ply in the $[0_2/90_8]_S$ was about 10 MPa, the strain changes were simply calculated by the experimental result of the $[90]_{16}$ at 10 MPa and classical laminate theory. Table3 shows the material properties of the CFRP used for this calculation. The initial residual stress were caused by temperature change from 180°C, the cure condition to 100°C, the test condition. The strain, ϵ_x was calculated by Equation (2) and (3). The strains due to physical aging $\epsilon_{x, PA}$ (experiment in the $[90]_{16}$ specimens), and $\epsilon_{y, PA}$ (=0), and $\epsilon_{z, PA}$ (=0) were added to the amount of residual strain in the laminates.

Fig.4 Residual strain changes by FBGs.

Fig.5 Strain changes in $[90]_{16}$ specimen.

$$\begin{Bmatrix} N_x \\ N_y \\ N_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \sum_{k=1}^n \begin{bmatrix} \bar{Q}_{11} & \bar{Q}_{12} & \bar{Q}_{16} \\ \bar{Q}_{12} & \bar{Q}_{22} & \bar{Q}_{26} \\ \bar{Q}_{16} & \bar{Q}_{26} & \bar{Q}_{66} \end{bmatrix} \int_{z_{k-1}}^{z_k} \begin{Bmatrix} \alpha_x \\ \alpha_y \\ \alpha_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} \Delta T + \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_{x,PA} \\ \varepsilon_{y,PA} \\ \varepsilon_{xy,PA} \end{Bmatrix} dz \quad (2)$$

$$\begin{Bmatrix} N_x \\ N_y \\ N_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} & A_{16} \\ A_{12} & A_{22} & A_{26} \\ A_{16} & A_{26} & A_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_x \\ \varepsilon_y \\ \varepsilon_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

Figure 7 shows the comparison of strain changes between experimental results and calculations with and without influence of physical aging. The decrease in the measured strain showed the influence of physical aging on the laminate strain. Since there was a good correlation between the measured strains and the calculated strain with the influence of physical aging, introduction of the influence is important for the calculation of small strain in the laminates. The balance of the material properties in the laminates including physical aging and/or stress relaxation will determine whether the strains were tensile or compressive.

4 Concluding remarks

- 1) Strain changes due to physical aging were measured by FBGs.
- 2) The strain change in 90° CFRP was largest because of resin shrinkage.
- 3) The strain changes were almost same with changes in laminates thickness.
- 4) Creep test results illustrated that it is important to consider the strain changes due to physical aging.

References

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Fig.6 Calculated creep modulus in $[90]_{16}$ specimen without physical aging.

Table3 Material properties used for calculation

0° modulus, E_L	152000	MPa
90° modulus, $E_T(0)$	6790.87	MPa
Laminate thickness	2.7	mm
0° CTE, α_L	-0.55 E-6	1/K
90° CTE, α_T	22.5 E-6	1/K
Tem. change, ΔT	-80	°C
Poisson' ratio, ν_{LT}	0.334	-
Poisson' ratio, ν_{TL}	0.018689	-
Shear modulus, G_{TZ}	2516	MPa

Fig. 7 Strain changes in $[0_2/90_8]_S$ specimen.